

IMPROVING THE AUDIT OF COMMODITY MATERIAL RESERVES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

Toshkulov Zafar Shamsiddinovich

Banking and finance academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14287642>

Commodity material reserves, including office supplies, IT equipment, and security-related materials, are essential for the smooth operations of commercial banks. While these reserves are not directly linked to revenue generation, their proper management and auditing ensure compliance with regulations, operational continuity, and reliable financial reporting. This thesis addresses the challenges faced in auditing these reserves and proposes solutions to improve the audit process using advanced tools and methodologies.

The importance of auditing commodity material reserves

Auditing commodity material reserves ensures the accuracy and transparency of financial records, reduces the risks of mismanagement, and aligns with regulatory requirements. Effective auditing allows banks to optimize the allocation and utilization of these resources, leading to cost-efficiency and informed decision-making. Moreover, robust audits support operational sustainability by identifying gaps in inventory management.

Challenges in auditing commodity material reserves

Auditing commodity material reserves presents several challenges. First, the complexity of managing diverse inventories across multiple branches increases the risk of errors and inconsistencies. Second, inconsistent valuation methods, such as the use of FIFO or weighted average cost, lead to discrepancies in financial reporting. Third, weak internal controls expose banks to fraud risks, including theft or misappropriation. Fourth, compliance with international standards like IFRS and local regulations complicates the audit process. Lastly, many banks rely on outdated systems that lack the efficiency required for modern auditing needs.

Technological integration

The integration of advanced technologies can significantly enhance the auditing of commodity material reserves. ERP systems provide real-time tracking and reporting of inventory, ensuring accurate reconciliation. AI tools help detect anomalies and automate routine auditing tasks, while blockchain technology adds transparency and ensures the immutability of transaction records, reducing fraud risks.

Risk-Based auditing

Risk-based auditing prioritizes high-risk areas, such as branches with significant inventory volumes or locations with a history of discrepancies. By conducting periodic risk assessments, banks can dynamically allocate audit resources where they are most needed, improving the effectiveness and efficiency of the audit process.

Standardized practices

Adopting standardized valuation and reporting methods across all branches ensures consistency in financial reporting. This includes establishing uniform formats for inventory documentation and reconciliation, which simplifies the review process and minimizes errors. Training inventory managers in these practices further strengthens the audit framework.

Strengthened internal controls

Robust internal controls are critical for managing and auditing commodity material reserves. Periodic physical inventory counts, restricted access to storage facilities, and clear procurement policies reduce the risks of mismanagement. These measures also provide reliable data that enhances the quality of audits and supports compliance with regulations.

Auditor training and competency

Equipping auditors with training in modern tools and regulatory frameworks ensures they are prepared to handle complex auditing tasks. Certifications such as Certified Internal Auditor (CIA) or Certified Information Systems Auditor (CISA) enhance their expertise, enabling them to utilize advanced technologies and address emerging challenges effectively.

Conclusion

Improving the accounting of commodity-material reserves in commercial banks is essential for operational excellence, cost efficiency, and compliance. By adopting modern technologies, standardizing practices, and strengthening internal controls, banks can overcome existing challenges and ensure the effective management of their reserves. These improvements contribute not only to financial stability but also to enhanced stakeholder confidence in the organization's operational integrity.

List of literature:

1. Arens, A. A., Elder, R. J., & Beasley, M. S. (2018). Auditing and Assurance Services: An Integrated Approach. Pearson Education.
2. Hayes, R., Dassen, R., Schilder, A., & Wallage, P. (2014). Principles of Auditing: An Introduction to International Standards on Auditing. Pearson Education.

3. Gelinias, U. J., Dull, R. B., & Wheeler, P. R. (2020). Accounting Information Systems. Cengage Learning.